

Synthesis and Mass Spectral Studies of Some 1-(2-Benzothiazolyl)-5-aryl-3-methylpyrazoles

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Sixteen new 1-(2-benzothiazolyl)-5-aryl-3-methylpyrazoles (I) have been synthesised by the condensation of 1-aryl-1,3-butanediones and 2-hydrazinobenzothiazoles. Bromination study of I ($R=R'=H$) in $Br_2/AcOH$ has revealed that electrophilic attack of bromine occurs in pyrazole ring at position 4. The mass spectral studies of these compounds involve fragmentation via three principal modes (a) fission of benzothiazole ring, (b) fission of pyrazole ring resulting in the loss of 2-benzothiazolyldiazonium radical and (c) fission of pyrazole ring with concomitant loss of CH_3CN from the molecular ion.

In view of antiinflammatory activity associated with various pyrazole and benzothiazole derivatives¹⁻³, it was considered worthwhile to undertake the synthesis and mass spectral studies of some 1-(2-benzothiazolyl)-5-aryl-3-methylpyrazoles (I).

Scheme 1

In the present study, the synthesis of I has been accomplished by a versatile method of pyrazole synthesis⁴ which involved condensation of 1-aryl-1,3-butanediones (III) and 2-hydrazinobenzothiazoles (II) under usual experimental conditions. β -Diketones (III) required for this purpose were readily obtained by Claisen condensation between ethyl acetate and respective acetophenones⁵, while different hydrazines (II) were prepared by treating the corresponding 2-chlorobenzothiazoles with hydrazine hydrate⁶⁻⁸.

The structures of the pyrazoles (I) were confirmed by their elemental analysis, ir, pmr and mass spectral data. IR spectra† did not show any absorption in

the region 1640-1700 cm^{-1} (absence of carbonyl group) and 3200-3400 cm^{-1} (absence of $-NHNH_2$). In the pmr spectrum of Ia (I, $R=R'=H$), the signals at δ 2.42, 6.4 and 7.3-8.05 are due to the presence of 3-H of CH_3 group, 1-H pyrazole proton at C-4 and 9-H aromatic protons, respectively.

The singlet at δ 2.42 in the pmr spectrum of the above-mentioned compound (Ia) is ascribed to a methyl group. However, this methyl group may be located at position 3 or 5 of the pyrazole moiety because of the following considerations. The attack of a hydrazine molecule can occur on either of the two carbonyl groups present in 1-aryl-1,3-butanediones. In case the carbonyl group adjacent to the methyl group is attacked, it will result in the formation of 1-(2-benzothiazolyl)-3-methyl-5-phenylpyrazole (Ia), whereas the product would be 1-(2-benzothiazolyl)-5-methyl-3-phenylpyrazole in case the attack has taken place at the carbonyl group adjacent to the phenyl ring.

However, it is reported in the literature that the carbonyl group adjacent to an alkyl group is relatively more reactive, e.g., benzoylacetone reacts with *p*-chlorophenylhydrazine to form 1-*p*-chlorophenyl-3-methyl-5-phenylpyrazole rather than 1-*p*-chlorophenyl-3-phenyl-5-methylpyrazole¹⁰. Similar results were obtained in the present case and the formation of 1-(2-benzothiazolyl)-3-methyl-5-phenylpyrazole has been confirmed by the study of the mass spectral data.

An inspection of the mass spectrum of Ia revealed that the most abundant fragment ion (54% at m/z

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† IR ν_{max}^{KBr} in cm^{-1} and chemical shift in δ ppm throughout the paper.

250) arises by the loss of methyl cyanide from the molecular ion (base peak, m/z 291). This type of fragmentation essentially requires the presence of methyl group at position 3 of the pyrazole ring. In the alternate structure having phenyl group at position 3, the pyrazole ring would have cleaved with the expulsion of phenyl cyanide. Mass spectra of other compounds (**Ii** and **Im**) were also characterised by the expulsion of methyl cyanide from the molecular ion.

Bromination of 1-(2-benzothiazolyl)-3-methyl-5-phenylpyrazole (**Ia**) has also been studied in $\text{Br}_2\text{-AcOH}$ to find out the exact site of attack of bromine. The possible sites for electrophilic attack of bromine are (a) C-4 of pyrazole ring, (b) *o/p*-positions of phenyl ring at C-5 of the pyrazole ring and (c) position 6 of benzothiazole ring. However, in the present study, bromination of **Ia** in $\text{Br}_2\text{-AcOH}$ at room temperature afforded mono-substituted product showing a single spot on tlc plate. The elemental analysis of brominated product correspond to molecular formula $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{SBr}$ which was further supported by its mass spectrum showing molecular ion at m/z 369/371 (Calcd. Mol. wt. 370). Singlet at δ 6.4 due to one proton at C-4 of pyrazole nucleus appearing in the pmr spectrum of the parent compound (**Ia**) disappeared in the brominated product (**IV**), which provides the conclusive evidence that electrophilic attack of bromine takes place at C-4 of the pyrazole nucleus. This observation was further supported by the fact that bromination of 3-phenyl-5-chloropyrazole results in the substitution of pyrazole ring at position 4¹¹.

Mass spectral studies :

The characteristic feature in the mass spectra of compounds (**I**) is the fission of the molecular ion *via* three principal modes, (a) fission of benzothiazole ring, (b) fission of pyrazole ring resulting in the loss of 2-benzothiazolyldiazonium radical and (c) fission of pyrazole ring with the concomitant loss of CH_3CN from the molecular ion. Mass spectrum of 1-(2-benzothiazolyl)-3-methyl-5-phenylpyrazole (**Ia**), for instance, shows molecular ion at m/z 291 appearing as the base peak. Fission of benzothiazole moiety yielded an ion at m/z 108 in accordance with the known fragmentation pattern of benzothiazole¹². The predominant fragmentation, however, involves the loss of CH_3CN from the molecular ion resulting in the formation of an intense ion at m/z 250. This ion further loses hydrogen radical and acetylene to yield ions at m/z 249 and 223, respectively. In a competing pathway, pyrazole ring suffers cleavage with the expulsion of 2-benzothiazolyldiazonium

radical from the molecular ion. The resultant ion at m/z 129 loses acetylene to yield an ion at m/z 103. This ion further undergoes a loss of acetylene giving phenyl cation at m/z 77. The cation at m/z 129 also undergoes a loss of propylene radical to give an intense peak of benzocyclopropenyl ion at m/z 90. All these processes are rationalized by the sequences outlined in Chart A.

Chart A

The above mentioned fragmentation has been confirmed by the study of mass spectra of compounds 1-(6-chloro-2-benzothiazolyl)-3-methyl-5-phenylpyrazole (**Im**) and 1-(6-methoxy-2-benzothiazolyl)-3-methyl-5-phenylpyrazole (**Ii**). For example, mass spectrum of **Im** revealed prominent ions having a chlorine atom at m/z 284/286, 283/285, 257/259 and 142/144 corresponding to the ions at m/z 250, 249, 223 and 108, respectively observed in the mass spectrum of **Ia** providing thereby a strong evidence for the similarity in the degradative sequence in both the compounds. In the mass spectrum of **Ii**, fragmentation pattern was slightly different. In this case, processes b and c are exactly parallel to those observed in compounds **Ia** and **Im**, whereas the path 'a' could not be exactly followed. In this case, the molecular ion undergoes loss of CH_3 radical followed by expulsion of CO to give an ion at m/z 278. This ion suffers a cleavage of pyrazole (by the loss of CH_3CN) and benzothiazole moieties yielding ions at m/z 237 and m/z 95, respectively. Significant mass spectral data of these three compounds are enlisted in Table 1.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. IR spectra in KBr were recorded

TABLE 1—SIGNIFICANT MASS SPECTRAL DATA OF 1-(6-SUBSTITUTED-2-BENZOTHAZOLYL)-5-ARYL-3-METHYLPYRAZOLES (I) (ARRANGED TO DISPLAY THE COINCIDENCE OF FRAGMENT IONS IN THE THREE COMPOUNDS)

m/z (% intensity)		
Ia	Ii	Iii
291 (100)	321 (100)	325/327 (100)
276 (28)	306 (84)	310/312 (18)
250 (54)	280 (49)	284/286 (45)
249 (10)	279 (13)	283/285 (7)
223 (33)	253 (22)	257/259 (27)
129 (7)	129 (17)	129 (17)
117 (14)	117 (25)	117 (5)
108 (9)	—	142/144 (22)
103 (14)	103 (23)	103 (21)
90 (14)	90 (16)	90 (21)
77 (23)	77 (5)	77 (31)
—	278 (13)	—
—	237 (10)	—
—	95 (8)	—

on a Beckman IR-20 spectrometer and pmr spectra on a Varian A-60 instrument using TMS as internal standard. Purity of the compounds was tested by tlc using silica gel G coated plates (21 × 20 cm²) of 0.5 mm thickness.

1-Aryl-1,3-butanediones (III)⁶ and 2-hydrazinobenzothiazoles⁶⁻⁹ were prepared as described in literature.

1-(2-Benzothiazolyl)-3-methyl-5-phenylpyrazoles (Ia): A mixture of 2-hydrazinobenzothiazole (1.65 g; 0.01 mole) and 1-phenyl-1,3-butanedione (1.62 g; 0.01 mole) was refluxed for 3 hr in ethanol (20 ml) containing a few drops of acetic acid. After keeping the reaction mixture at room temperature for 4-5 hr, the separated solid was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 118-20° (75%). PMR: 2.45 (s, 3H, CH₃); 6.4 (s, 1H, pyrazole proton) and 7.3-8.05 (m, 9H, aromatic protons). MS: M⁺, m/z 291 (Calcd. Mol. wt. 291) (Found: N, 14.52; S, 10.58. C₁₇H₁₃N₃S requires N, 14.43; S, 10.99%). Other compounds of the series were prepared following a similar procedure (Table 2).

Bromination of 1-(2-benzothiazolyl)-3-methyl-5-phenylpyrazole: Finely powdered 1-(2-benzothiazolyl)-3-methyl-5-phenylpyrazole (Ia) (2.9 g; 0.01 mole) in acetic acid (10 ml) was taken in a conical flask. Bromine (1.7 g) in acetic acid (5 ml) was added slowly from dropping funnel and with constant shaking to ensure thorough mixing. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 2 hr with occasional shaking. The reaction product was poured into 50 ml of water. The mixture was stirred well for 1 hr and filtered to give IV which was crystallised from benzene, m.p. 152-53° (67.5%). PMR: 2.45 (s, 3H, CH₃), 7.5 (m, 9H, aromatic protons). MS: M⁺, m/z 369/371 (Calcd. Mol. wt.

TABLE 2—CHARACTERISATION DATA OF 1-(2-BENZOTHAZOLYL)-5-ARYL-3-METHYLPYRAZOLES (I)*

Com- pound	R	R'	m.p. °C	yield (%)	Mol. formula
Ia	H	H	118	75	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃ S
Ib	H	OCH ₃	214	78	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ OS
Ic	H	Cl	180	68	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₃ ClS
Id	H	Br	130	71	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₃ BrS
Ie	CH ₃	H	144	70	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ S
If	CH ₃	OCH ₃	146	77	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ OS
Ig	CH ₃	Cl	172	73	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₃ ClS
Ih	CH ₃	Br	150	75	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₃ BrS
Ii	OCH ₃	H	128	67	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ N ₃ OS
Ij	OCH ₃	OCH ₃	140	73	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₂ S
Ik	OCH ₃	Cl	182	70	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₃ ClOS
Il	OCH ₃	Br	164	78	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₃ BrOS
Im	Cl	H	132	71	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ N ₃ ClS
In	Cl	OCH ₃	143	67	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ N ₃ ClOS
Io	Cl	Cl	196	64	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₃ Cl ₂ S
Ip	Cl	Br	154	65	C ₁₇ H ₁₁ N ₃ ClBrS

*Satisfactory N, S analyses were obtained for all the compounds. Solvent of crystallization: Ia - Ip = Ethanol.

370) (Found: N, 11.40; Br, 21.56. C₁₇H₁₂N₃BrS requires N, 11.35; Br, 21.62%).

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References

- K. KATO, M. HORI, O. OHATANI, K. IZUMI, T. KITAMIKADO, H. ASAI and S. SUGIURA, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1977, **20**, 80.
- S. SUGIURA, K. KATO, S. OHNO, O. OHATANI and T. WAKAYAMA, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1977, **97**, 719.
- W. E. GOVNE, "Medicinal Chemistry", (Ed.) A. BURGER, Wiley Interscience, New York, 1970, Vol. II, p. 953; T. Y. SHEN, "Antiinflammatory Agents", (Eds.) R. A. SCHERRER and M. W. WHITEHOUSE, Academic Press, New York, 1974, Vol. I, p. 179.
- T. L. JACOBS, "Heterocyclic Compounds", (Ed.) R. C. ELDERFIELD, John Wiley and Sons, Inc., New York, 1957, Vol. 5, p. 48.
- (a) A. I. VOGEL, "Practical Organic Chemistry", 1971, p. 865.
(b) C. R. HAUSER, F. W. SWAMER and B. I. RINGLES, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 4023.
- N. Z. DROZDOV and V. I. STAVROSKAYA, *J. Gen. Chem. (USSR)*, 1937, **7**, 2813; *Chem. Abs.*, 1938, **32**, 2940.
- N. S. MOON, *U. S. Pat.*, 2,469,697, 1949; *Chem. Abs.*, 1949, **43**, 6670.
- L. KATZ, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 4007.
- V. R. RAO and V. R. SRINIVASAN, *Experientia*, 1964, **20**, 200; *Chem. Abs.*, 1964, **60**, 14496a.
- W. J. BARRY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 1171.
- L. A. PAQUETTE, "Principles of Modern Heterocyclic Chemistry", W. A. BENJAMIN, Inc., N. Y., Amsterdam, 1968, p. 196.
- H. OJURA and S. SUGIMOTO, *Org. Mass Spectrum*, 1970, **3**, 1341.